

MULTIDIRECTIONALLY REINFORCED CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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Introduction

Graphite is an attractive material for high temperature applications based on properties such as high sublimation temperature, improved strength at elevated temperatures, thermal stress resistance, high heat of ablation, and chemical inertness. In its bulk forms of polycrystalline graphite and pyrolytic graphite, it has been utilized with only limited success for aerospace applications because of low strength, low strain-to-failure, variability in properties, and fabrication difficulties associated with relatively large structures. The advent of carbon fiber technology has substantially increased the potential of graphite materials, initially as an approach to improving large-scale fabricability and subsequently, with the development of high strength and high modulus fibers, as a means of increasing the strength properties along with an improved capability of tailoring properties. Consequently, carbon/carbon composites, from their early stages (1,2), have undergone significant development, primarily for applications such as re-entry protection systems (3-9), propulsion systems (10-14), and space systems (15,16).

The original carbon/carbon materials were based on two dimensional (2-D) reinforcements. These materials exhibited an improvement in strength over monolithic graphite in the plane of reinforcements, but showed deficiencies in strength normal to this plane where no reinforcement existed. The development of multidirectionally reinforced materials have overcome this problem (17). In-house efforts at Fiber Materials, Inc., (FMI) have led to the development of materials reinforced in three (3-D), four (4-D), five (5-D), seven (7-D) and eleven (11-D) directions. Of these reinforcement concepts the 3-D high axial strength and 7-D isotropic are the more familiar. Any of these structures woven with graphite yarn can be processed to form dense high strength carbon fiber reinforced carbon matrix (carbon/carbon) composites.

This paper will describe the woven structure and densification processing required to manufacture multidirectional carbon/carbon composites. Also a summary of properties typical of early and current state-of-the art composites will be presented.

Multidirectional Woven Substrates

Fibrous substrates can be woven to attain properties desired for specific reinforced composite systems such as carbon/carbon. Thermal, mechanical and physical properties of the composite may be enhanced by the appropriate design of weaving parameters such as fiber orientation, volume fraction of fiber in required directions, fiber spacing, woven density, yarn packing efficiency, and fiber selection (17).

Fiber Selection to Meet Design Requirements

Fiber selection is a function of the application and environment for which the composite is designed. Some examples of fiber-matrix application combinations are listed in Table I.

Table I. Typical Fiber-Matrix Application Combinations

Fiber	Matrix	Application
Silica	Silica	Electro Magnetic Windows
Boron Nitride	Boron Nitride	Electro Magnetic Windows
Silica	Phenolic	Ablative Shield
Graphite	Graphite	Ablative Shield
Graphite	Epoxy	Structural
Graphite	Aluminum	Structural
Fiberglass	Polyester	Structural

Once the fiber type has been selected, based on the application of the final composite structure, the fibers must be obtained in a useful form. The most common form is a yarn; a yarn being a continuous length of plied fibers held together by fiber friction obtained by twisting or by an added coating or both. Groups of similar or dissimilar yarns may be plied or twisted as required to meet the design objectives of the woven structure. An example of a possible plied yarn formed by combining dissimilar yarn/fiber types is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Yarn Plying and Twisting

Small amounts of yarn coatings or finishes are required for ease of yarn handling during weaving operations. Also, yarn coatings are often required for subsequent impregnation to achieve compatibility between fiber matrix. The optimum situation occurs when the required compatible coating is also sufficient for handling during the weaving operations.

Design of Woven Structures

A useful form of interwoven yarns for structural reinforcement of composite materials is two-dimensional fabric. Fabrics are characterized by

the spacing between adjacent yarns, bundle size, percent of yarn in each direction, yarn packing efficiency and the complexity of the interwoven pattern. A schematic of a plain weave fabric and the five harness satin weave are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - 2-D Fabric

The satin construction offers the advantage of the floating yarns which contribute more strength to a composite because of the straight lengths. This factor results in increased tensile performance over the plain weave fabric.

The two directional yarn orientation fabric can be further tailored for certain applications where a third direction of yarn orientation is required. A typical three-dimensional (3-D) fabric is schematically shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Single Layer 3-D Fabric

The 3-D fabric offers the benefit of having straight lengths of yarn in two normal directions with the third direction interlooping to bind the other directions in position. The yarn bundle size, spacing between adjacent yarn bundles, yarn packing efficiency, and the percent of yarn in each direction also characterize the 3-D fabric design. As shown in Figure 3, the space between adjacent yarns is controlled by the bundle size or diameter of the yarn in the orthogonal direction. This means that the smallest center-to-center yarn spacings are obtained by using yarns with the smallest diameter.

Design of 3-D Orthogonal Structures

Structures with reinforcing yarns oriented in multiple directions may be designed to meet application requirements. A typical 3-D orthogonal structure is shown in Figure 4. The same design parameters apply to this type structure as to the 2-D and 3-D type fabrics. Schematics of various weave configurations are shown in Figure 5 to illustrate the design versatility that 3-D orthogonal structures offer.

Figure 4 - 3-D Orthogonal Weave

Figure 5 - Typical 3-D Block Constructions

Typical yarn spacings, woven bulk densities, and volume fraction distribution resulting from variations in yarn plies for two selected graphite yarn types are shown in Table II.

Bulk densities, percent fiber volume fraction, and yarn spacings can be mathematically calculated knowing the linear density of the yarn. The

Table II. Weave Characteristics of Typical Woven Preforms

Thornel* 50										
Bulk Density (gms/cc)	No. of Yarn Bundles			Center-to-Center Bundle Spacing				VfX	VfY	VfZ
				X,Y		Z				
	X	Y	Z	(Inch)	(mm)	(Inch)	(mm)			
.64	1	1	1	.022	0.56	.023	0.58	34%	34%	32%
.75	1	1	2	.028	0.71	.023	0.58	24	24	52
.68	2	2	1	.040	1.02	.023	0.58	35	35	30
.80	2	2	6	.027	0.69	.040	1.02	25	25	50
Thornel* 75										
Bulk Density (gms/cc)	No. of Yarn Bundles			Center-to-Center Bundle Spacing				VfX	VfY	VfZ
				X,Y		Z				
	X	Y	Z	(Inch)	(mm)	(Inch)	(mm)			
.70	1	1	2	.022	0.56	.023	0.58	26%	26%	48%
.65	2	2	1	.033	0.84	.023	0.58	37	37	26
.72	2	2	2	.042	1.07	.023	0.58	25	25	50
Boron Nitride										
Bulk Density (gms/cc)	No. of Yarn Bundles			Center-to-Center Bundle Spacing				VfX	VfY	VfZ
				X,Y		Z				
	X	Y	Z	(Inch)	(mm)	(Inch)	(mm)			
1.06	2	2	2	.062	1.57	.125	3.18	40%	40%	40%
1.21	2	2	4	.077	1.96	.125	3.18	31	31	38
.93	2	2	2	.080	2.03	.125	3.18	38	38	24
Silica										
Bulk Density (gms/cc)	No. of Yarn Bundles			Center-to-Center Bundle Spacing				VfX	VfY	VfZ
				X,Y		Z				
	X	Y	Z	(Inch)	(mm)	(Inch)	(mm)			
1.28	4	4	30	.040	1.09	.090	2.29	20%	20%	60%
1.55	6	6	10	.037	9.94	.090	2.29	32	32	36
1.36	2	2	2	.028	0.71	.040	1.02	28	28	44

*Registered Trade Mark-Union Carbide Corporation.

balanced 3-D orthogonal structure has a maximum packing potential of 75% assuming solid yarns with a square or rectangular cross-section. The remaining 25% of the unit cell volume is void.

Since yarns generally do not pack to a square cross-section and the filaments comprising the yarn bundle do not pack solid, the achievable packing efficiency is dependent on the ease of handling of the yarn. For example, an easier handling silica yarn can pack from 60-65% while the fragile graphite yarns pack from 45-50% of the yarn density. The porosity between the filaments of the yarn and the 25-plus percent void area is filled by the matrix material for translation of fiber properties and design to the

application.

Yarn packing efficiency is a limiting design parameter in woven substrates. Due to inherent pore areas, voids and interfiber air space, the following is always true:

Specific Volume of Structure > Specific Volume of Yarn

Bulk Density of Structure < Bulk Density of Yarn

Most woven textile structures are composed of more than 40% air space. In general, geometrical weave design parameters determine the porosity of a woven substrate. However, the total porosity of the substrate depends directly on the ability of individual filaments that comprise the yarn to pack efficiently. Yarns comprised of filaments with circular cross-sections will demonstrate a higher packing efficiency than yarn comprised of filaments with irregular cross-sections.

In general, 3-D structures woven from circular filament yarns (e.g., quartz and glass) have maximum yarn packing efficiencies in the range of 80-86%. Preforms woven from yarns with irregular cross-sections (e.g., rayon precursor graphite) will have characteristic maximum yarn packing efficiencies of 60-66%.

Figure 6 illustrates high density yarn bundles in the 3-D structure. Yarn interfaces are easily recognizable due to yarn twist. Figure 7 shows individual circular fiber packing for silica fibers and in localized areas close hexagonal packing (91% efficiency) is demonstrated.

Figure 6 - High Density Axial Yarn Bundles

Note Packing of Twisted 4 Ply Yarns
and Interfiber/Interyarn Air Space

For some applications, an important design parameter is the size and the dispersion of the void pocket. The infiltration of a large void pocket with impregnant that will undergo shrinkage during cure and/or pyrolysis is more difficult than filling a small void. One such application is for ablative composites where the small and well dispersed void cells approach the grain size of solid graphite. For this application, yarns with small

500X

Typical High Density Filament Packing
Filament Dia. $\approx 10\mu$

500X

Typical Twisted Yarn Filament
Interface

Note Localized Areas of Hexagonal Close Packing

Figure 7 - Silica Fiber Packing

diameters spaced closely together will result when using a weave design having this parameter.

Several weave modifications to the basic 3-D orthogonal design are available in order to form a more isotropic woven structure. Woven preforms with 5, 7 or 11 directions of reinforcement aid in obtaining a composite with isotropic properties. The 5-D design (Figure 8) demonstrates the basic 3-D structure with the addition of two reinforcement directions in

Figure 8 - 5-D Construction

Figure 9 - Typical "Across the Corners"
Diagonals 7-D Construction Type 1

Figure 10 -- Typical "Across the Face" Diagonals, 7-D Construction. Type II

Figure 11 - Typical "Across the Corners" Diagonals; Typical "Across the Face" Diagonals, 11-D Construction

the X-Y plane. This weave configuration will give + 45° reinforcement in the X-Y plane along with the axial (Z) direction of reinforcement. In order to enhance composite properties between the planes of reinforcement, diagonal yarns are introduced to a modified 3-D structure. Diagonal reinforcement across the four corners of the 3-D block structure is shown in Figure 9. This, combined with the baseline 3-D, produces one type of 7-D preform. Another type of 7-D structure contains diagonal yarns across the faces of the preform as shown in Figure 10. The same degrees of 3-D design tailorability apply to the 7-D structure with respect to preform packing efficiency, preform density, and percent of directional reinforcement. Table 3 describes examples of available 7-D constructions. A combination of the 3-D base structure, diagonal across the corners and diagonals across the face will produce a third type of isotropic woven structure with 11 directions of reinforcement. The 11-D structure is shown in Figure 11.

Table III. Various 7-D Construction Parameters

Ends T-50			Volume Fract. (ea)			Density
D	X,Y	Z	D	X,Y	Z	gm/cc
3	4	4	12	17.3	17.3	.52
4	4	4	13.8	14.9	14.9	.62
4	4	6	12.9	13.9	20.5	.65
4	1	16	11.3	3.0	48.7	.75

Complex shapes such as a turbine blade configuration (Figure 12) can be woven utilizing current weave design technology. The 3-D orthogonal design is unique for the combined stresses that the blade must withstand.

The design of cylinders and shapes of revolution, i.e. frusta, ogive, etc., with reinforcing yarns oriented in three directions is based on the same varying parameters as fabric and blocks, i.e., yarn bundle size, adjacent yarn spacing, and the percentage of yarn in each direction. How-

Figure 12 - 3-D Woven Orthogonal Turbine Blade

ever, the orientation of the yarns is not truly orthogonal, but rather as depicted in Figure 13.

These yarn directions are termed axial (A), radial (R), and circumferential (C). Because of the "pie" shaped unit cell, an additional design feature, peculiar to cylindrical configurations, must be employed to ensure uniformity of the weave design (Figure 14). As the radial yarns converge towards the ID of the cylinder, axial yarn bundles must increase in diameter from the ID to the OD to compensate and maintain a uniform density structure.

Another design concept to compensate for the "pie" shaped unit cell is to taper a radial position in a regular pattern so as to maintain a constant axial yarn bundle diameter from ID to OD. This method also maintains a constant woven density from ID to OD.

Woven structures may also be designed to shapes such as the frustum

Figure 13 - 3-D Cylindrical Weave Yarn Orientation

Axial Yarn Compensation From ID To OD
Axial Yarn Diameter Varies

Radial Yarn Compensation From ID To OD
Axial Yarn Diameter Constant
Figure 14

of a cone. Axial yarns can be oriented to the same half angle as the cone angle. The diametral change from the aft end to the forward end involves another design parameter. In order to maintain constant yarn spacings and uniform density from the aft to the forward end, axial yarns can be tapered. The same construction variables and resulting weave parameters possible for cylindrical weaves can also be designed for frustum shapes. Variations of the cylinder frustum, namely the ogive and the cylinder with a hemispherical end cap integrally woven, can also be 3-D woven with currently available technology (Figure 15).

Matrix Processing of Multidirectionally Reinforced Carbon/Carbon Composites

General

The most widely used approach to introducing a carbon matrix into the multidirectionally fibrous preforms described above is through the impregnation of the preform with an organic material and subsequent carbonization

Ogive with Flange

Cylinder with Flange
and Hemispherical End Cap

Figure 15 - Typical 3-D Preform Shapes

of the resultant composite under an inert atmosphere. The conventional densification process is conducted at atmospheric pressure and must be repeated several times to reduce the porosity to an acceptable level (9). The multiplicity of cycles and the ensuing long process times are the result of: 1) low carbon yield from the carbon-bearing liquid impregnant, 2) premature flow of the impregnant from the pores during carbonization, 3) lack of pressure to uniformly impregnate a composite, 4) large volumetric shrinkage of the impregnant, 5) slow carbonization cycles required to obtain isothermal heating and 6) the need to minimize the effects of gas evolution from the carbonizing impregnant (18).

As a result of these limiting characteristics, a technique was developed by Cook and Lambdin (20) which utilized isostatic pressure to effectively impregnate carbon composites during the melting and heating phase of the carbonization cycle. This work showed that graphite fibrous composites with a pitch impregnant could be successfully carbonized in a sealed can with 95% conversion of the carbon precursor impregnant to solid carbon. Further work in the U.S. and Europe has shown that this pressure impregnation-carbonization (PIC) technique has applications and advantages in the densification of various multidirectional reinforced carbon/carbon composites(14,18,19).

Fitzer and co-workers (21) in Germany have also confirmed the utility of the pressure carbonization technique. Dr. Fitzer has also shown the extreme pressures (15,000 psi, 103.4 MPa) utilized by Cook and Lambdin are not required to obtain the increased carbon yield.

A summary of Fiber Materials, Inc.'s studies (18) on the effect of pressure on coke yield of petroleum pitch is presented in Figure 16. These results indicate that carbonization pressures in the range of 1000 to 10,000 psi (6.9 - 68.9 MPa) are sufficient to achieve high coke yields.

Pressure Impregnation Carbonization (PIC) Processing

PIC processing of carbon/carbon composites is carried out in Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) equipment that has been specifically designed for this application. In addition to increased coke yields, the process offers

Figure 16 - Effect of Pressure Carbonization On Coke Yield for Petroleum Pitch

Table IV.

Effects of Pressure on the Densification Rate for Pitch Impregnated Carbon/Carbon Composites

Pressure		Coke Yield	Density (g/cc)	
(psi)	(MPa)		Initial	Final
ATM.	ATM.	51%	1.62	1.65
1,000	6.9	81%	1.51	1.58
7,000	51.7	88%	1.59	1.71
		89%	1.71	1.80
15,000	103.4	90%	1.66	1.78

other advantages that contribute to efficiency and reliability. Table IV presents the confirming data which compares the results of PIC cycles at several pressure levels. For a typical petroleum pitch, the standard condition (1 atmosphere) coking yield is 51 weight percent. However, the carbon content for such a pitch is usually greater than 90 percent. Therefore, a significant amount of the available carbon is lost during carbonization which results in a smaller density increase for the composite. By the application of a gas overpressure, the more volatile compounds formed within the heated pitch are prevented from evaporating and very likely form into higher molecular weight polyaromatics. As shown in Table IV, the coking yields increased to about 90 percent, which resulted in a significant increase in the composite density.

The PIC technique as carried out at FMI is shown, schematically, in Figure 17. A preform to be densified is initially vacuum-pressure impregnated using a hot pitch transfer system and carbonized while submerged

Figure 17 - Densification of C/C Material

in the pitch impregnant. This initial cycle is usually not performed under pressure to prevent damage or distortion to the preform. After machining, the impregnation is repeated and the part, submerged in excess pitch, is sealed in a thin wall stainless steel container. This prepares the composite for a PIC cycle. The container is placed in a hot isostatic press and heated at a programmed rate to 550-650°C, while the pressure is increased and maintained at pressures ranging from 1,000 to 15,000 psi (6.89 to 103.4 MPa). A typical cycle requires about 24 hours. The PIC process is followed by graphitization after the parts are removed from the container. This complete cycle is repeated to increase the density as shown in Figure 18. A densification curve for a similar composite densified by impregnation and carbonization at atmospheric pressure is included for comparison.

Figure 18 - Densification of Fine Weave C/C Composites

The rate of densification, as shown in Figure 18 is dependent upon; 1) the type of impregnant, 2) the coking yield of the impregnant, 3) the volume of porosity open to the impregnant and 4) the degree of filling of this porosity. Increased coking yield was initially considered the single most important advantage of the PIC technique. However, as composites were developed with smaller and more tortuous porosity, the advantage of the isostatic pressure during the impregnation phase of a PIC cycle was realized. As the pitch impregnant melts and expands, the isostatic pressure on the container maintains a compressive force on the pitch and thus prevents run-out from pores. In fact, the pressure improves the uniformity of pore filling as the viscosity of the petroleum pitch decreases with increasing temperature. This results in a more uniform composite microstructure as the PIC cycles are repeated.

Performance Data

Property data typical of early 3-D carbon/carbon block material using low pressure processing techniques are given in Table V (22). ATJ-S graphite data is included for comparison. Typical hoop tensile properties of various 3-D carbon/carbon composites that have been fabricated in cylindrical configuration are given in Table VI (23).

Current state-of-the-art for densification of high density, high strength multidirectionally reinforced carbon/carbon block materials involves PIC processing as discussed earlier. Table VII summarizes the pre-

Table V.
 Typical Properties of 3-D Carbon/Carbon Block Material
 Compared To Polycrystalline Graphite

	Temperature °C	ATJ-S Graphite with Grain*	3-D Carbon/Carbon Axial*
Density (g/cc)	24	1.83	1.65
Porosity (%)		9	10.5
Tensile Strength, MPa	24	39.0	103.4
	2485	54.4	68.9
Tensile Modulus, GPa	24	11.5	41.3
	2485	11.0	10.3
Tensile Strain-to- Failure %	24	0.4	0.3
	2485	2.0	2.7
Flexure Strength, MPa	24	42.0	96.5
	2485	72.3	103.4
Compressive Strength, MPa	24	88.9	82.7
	2485	182.0	158.5
Compressive Modulus, GPa	24	6.6	22.7
	2485	6.8	12.4
Thermal Conductivity, Watt/m ² K	260	114.2	55.4
	2485	46.7	24.2
Thermal Expansion, m/m x 10 ⁻³	TO 538	3.0	0.2
	TO 2485	11.5	4.7

*Major test axis is parallel to major crystalline or reinforcing plane.
 reference 22

Table VI.
 Typical Hoop Tensile Properties of Various Carbon/Carbon
 Compared to Carbon Phenolic

	Ultimate Hoop Strength, MPa	Elastic Modulus, GPa	Percent Total Strain
3-D Carbon/Phenolic	190	90	0.2
3-D Carbon/Carbon	164	99	0.16
Filament Wound- CVD Carbon/Carbon	73	40	0.24
Felt-CVD Carbon/Carbon	18	9	0.53

reference 23

form characteristics and general processing information for a typical 3-D carbon/carbon composite designed as 2-2-6. The construction of this preform is illustrated in Figure 5. For this particular composite the preform was supplied by FMI and the densification process was carried out at Battelle Columbus Laboratories (BCL). Mechanical and thermal properties of the fully densified 3-D carbon/carbon composites are given in Tables VIII and IX (19). The improved properties and high density as compared to early materials (Table V) are reflected in these data.

The high strength and modulus of the 3-D carbon/carbon composites offer advantages for structural applications. However, another significant advantage that 3-D carbon/carbon composites possess over polycrystalline graphite is in fracture behavior. Many investigators have commented on the "non-brittle" fracture behavior exhibited by carbon/carbon composites. This is illustrated in Figure 19 where the typical

Table IX. 3-D Carbon/Carbon Typical Thermal Properties

	Z	Direction	X-Y
Density, gm/cm ³		1.9	
Thermal Conductivity, W K ⁻¹ m ⁻¹ (Btu-in/hr-ft ² -°F)			
R.T.	20.5 (143)		12.4 (86)
1900°K (3000°F)	5.0 (35)		3.7 (26)
Thermal Expansion, m m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹			
R.T.	0		0
1900°K (3000°F)	3		4
3000°K (4950°F)	8		11
reference 19			
NOTE: Preform and process information in Table VII			

Figure 19 - Typical Load Deflection Curve for 3-D Carbon/Carbon Compared to ATJ-S Graphite

Reference 9

Advanced propulsion systems have generated a need for materials which are more erosion resistant, with increased dimensional stability and less susceptibility to thermostructural failure during multiple restarts. Representative applications include nozzles, thrust chambers, and ramjet combustion liners. Laramee and Canfield (13), who have reported on an extensive evaluation program, state the advantages of carbon/carbon systems lie in simpler design concepts and reduce nozzle weight and volume. Parmee has estimated a total weight savings of 30 to 50% if the rocket nozzle is designed completely in a carbon/carbon composite (11). Choury (25) has reported on ablation rates for several carbon/carbon nozzle materials, the 3-D carbon/carbon material exhibiting 29% less erosion than the best of the remaining materials.

Other applications for carbon/carbon are also being developed. Disk-brake systems made from carbon/carbon composites have undergone extensive development (26-28). The use of these materials for turbine disk and blade components is under evaluation. Another application has been hot-pressing dies (29). The advantages of carbon/carbon for this application are that larger parts can be fabricated, a longer use life can be obtained, and

higher pressing pressures can be utilized. The use of carbon/carbon materials for high-temperature ducting systems, components for nuclear rocket engines, and nuclear reactors are also under consideration. Electrical contacts, hot seals, and bearing materials for special design problems have also been mentioned as possible applications.

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